

9th International Conference on Information Technology Convergence and Services (ITCS 2020)

November 21~22, 2020, Zurich, Switzerland

<https://cst2020.org/itcs/index.html>

Call for Papers

9th International Conference on Information Technology Convergence and Services (ITCS 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Information Technology Convergence and Services. The Conference looks for significant contributions to all major fields of the Computer Science and Information Technology in theoretical and practical aspects. The aim of the conference is to provide a platform to the researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Advanced IT Bio/Medical Engineering
- Bioinformatics and applications
- Business and Information Systems
- Cloud computing
- Convergence in Information Technology Security
- Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery
- Digital convergence
- Electronic Commerce, Business and Management
- Grid and Cloud Computing
- Intelligent Robotics and Autonomous Agents
- Hardware and Software Design
- Health and Medical Informatics
- Hybrid information technology
- Intelligent communications and networks
- IT-based Convergence Technology and Service
- Multimedia convergence
- Smart Card and RFID Technologies
- Soft Computing and Intelligent Systems
- Social and Business Aspects of Convergence IT
- Ubiquitous Computing and Embedded Systems
- Recent Trends in Computing & Information technology

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **August 29, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **ITCS 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journal.

- [International Journal of Information Technology Convergence and Services\(IJITCS\)](#)
- [International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Applications\(IJCSEA\)](#)

- [International Journal of Advanced Information Technology \(IJAIT\)](#)
- [Advanced Computing: An International Journal \(ACIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology \(IJCEIT\)](#)
- [International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques \(IJIST\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)](#)^{New}- ESCI-Thomson Reuters Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : August 29, 2020**
- Authors Notification : October 05, 2020
- Registration & camera – Ready Paper Due : October 13, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : itcs@cst2020.org (or) itcsconf@yahoo.com

Submission System

<https://cst2020.org/submission/index.php>